

Computational load management strategies in cell-free-based, converged-optical-wireless 6G networks

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Abstract—The evolution of the telecommunication networks towards their 6th generation has emerged new research directions in order to deal with the challenges that are posed by the high-complexity of the new infrastructure. In this new era, the structuring of the network management infrastructure is a complex endeavor that should efficiently control both communication and computational resources. In this paper, we present a set of strategies for managing the computational load in a cell-free-based, converged optical-wireless 6G network. The proposed approaches target to control the computational load of a cell-free network, by either compressing the load by considering load-thresholds, or offloading the load to the SDN controller of the fixed network. Both strategies are mathematically formulated by considering traffic-engineering formulas, while their performance is evaluated by comparing analytical results with corresponding results from a baseline scenario, where no load control strategies are applied. Moreover, the proposed analysis can be applied in order to determine the capacity of the network controllers that is required in order to guarantee pre-determined Quality of Service requirements.

Index Terms—computational load, SDN controller, cell-free, converged optical-wireless networks, 6G networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The radical increase of telecommunication traffic demands has exercised significant pressure to the networking industry towards evolving to a low-latency, high-throughput, and low-energy-consumption infrastructure, while also facing the higher requirements in terms of sustainability and energy efficiency [1]. This evolution towards the 6th generation (6G) of communication networks can be achieved by incorporating novel networking architectures and disruptive communication technologies, as well as intelligent network management schemes that are able to optimally orchestrate the available networking and computational resources in an economic and ecological fashion [2].

The emergence of new types of applications and use-cases, such as multi-sensory extended reality, industrial automation/robotics, and autonomous mobility require the utilization of a robust framework that is able to confront their diverse requirements in terms of data-rate, latency, reliability and per-user performance metrics [3]. The new network infrastructure should be able to incorporate diverse network concepts and

technological aspects, in order to ensure economic developments, reliability, and increased energy efficiency. Thus, vital developments are required both in the network design level, as well as in the network management level, in order to support highly dynamic traffic, achieve energy reduction, and provide cost-effective, multi-level resource pooling [4]. In detail, the network should provide connectivity to multiple distributed edge nodes and to a multitude of access points that are coordinated by entities in a low-cost and near-zero-latency manner. In parallel, a unified and hierarchical infrastructure is indispensable, targeting to provide an intelligent, joint management of communication, computation and storage resources [5]. Moreover, the support of multiple tenants should be followed by the application of mechanisms for resourceful and efficient network management, which would play a vital role in enabling various use-cases and industry verticals targeted in 6G systems [6].

Having in mind the abovementioned challenges, in this paper, we consider a 6G network configuration that targets to interconnect a massive number of Access Points (APs) by utilizing the Cell-Free (CF) concept [7]. A converged optical-wireless configuration is assumed for the interconnection of scalable CF networks with the regional network [8]. In this way, an optical-based fronthaul network is utilized for the interconnection of multiple CF Distribution Units (DUs), thus ensuring a reliable support of dense Radio-Unit (RU) deployment, and unlocking the potential of user-centric, cell-free deployments in 6G networks [9]. At the regional edge segment, Software-Defined-Networking (SDN) controllers provide intelligent traffic management and load offloading/balancing among different segments of the network; the latter functions can be employed via an SDNi interface; this configuration can offer a high degree of flexibility, by allowing network resources to be dynamically shared among diverse network segments [10].

The main contribution of this paper focuses on the mathematical investigation of computational load strategies that are applied to a CF-based, converged optical-wireless 6G network. Specifically, the target of the proposed analysis is to reduce (or even eliminate) the probability that a request for

servicing a network function at the system’s SDN controller is rejected due to the unavailability of computational resources. The first control strategy, the threshold strategy, considers resource thresholds that gradually reduce the computational requirements of the service requests, while, at the same time, increase their service time. The second control strategy, the overflow strategy, considers a second SDN controller that is used in order to provide support to other users (e.g. Fiber-To-the-Home (FTTH) users), where service-requests that cannot be executed at the first controller due to the unavailability of resources, are forwarded to the second controller. The performance of the proposed strategies is evaluated by comparing analytical results with corresponding results from a baseline strategy, where no load control methods are applied. In all cases, the proposed analysis considers that the service requests may belong to different service-classes, with diverse computational requirements, request-arrival processes and service times. Moreover, the analysis of the performance of the proposed strategies utilizes well-known teletraffic models that have reduced complexity due to their recursive nature; this approach validates the robustness of the proposed analysis.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the network architecture and its main components. Section III presents the mathematical formulation of the load management procedure under the three considered scenarios, namely the baseline, threshold, and overflow scenario. Section IV is the evaluation section, while Section V concludes this paper.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

We consider a converged optical-wireless network configuration that incorporates the CF concept at the radio site, as it is illustrated in Fig. 1. RUs are interconnected with the DUs by considering fronthaul links that follow a bus topology, as in the case of Radio Stripes [11]. At the regional edge domain, an optical network in order to interconnect a distributed edge infrastructure with data centres structured in two tiers, featuring nodes at both the regional-edge and radio-edge domains. Intelligent functions of the control plane of the RAN are incorporated into the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). RIC is responsible for controlling and optimizing functions related to the Radio Resource Management (RRM) and the Self-Organizing Network (SON). The required SDN functions are hosted by the Near-Real Time (Near-RT) RIC, in order to provide near real-time reaction to traffic variations.

In parallel, the proposed network architecture considers an optical midhaul network, which interconnects regional edge nodes through a ring configuration. This configuration constitutes a Fixed-Mobile-Convergence (FMC) solution since it enables the access in shared resources to both fixed applications such as Fiber-To-the-Home (FTTH) and mobile applications being executed at the Radio Edge. The FMC solution is implemented by considering PtMP configurations (e.g. Passive Optical Networks) for interconnecting the different segments of the network. Therefore, both fixed and mobile users can share the same regional network infrastructure, while they are both served by the same core network. The traffic aggregation

Fig. 1. A cell-free-based, converged-optical-wireless 6G network.

of this infrastructure is executed at the regional edge under the control of the SDN controller located at the Near-RT RIC. For the control of the transport network, a Software Defined Transport Network (SDTN) controller is considered for the traffic aggregation control at the regional edge nodes, while it can dynamically configure various parameters based on the traffic variations, e.g. during heavy traffic periods exploiting the resources of another network segment; this can be achieved through the interconnection of the Near-RT RIC with the SDTN, through an SDNi interface.

III. MODEL DESCRIPTION

We consider the aforementioned network architecture, which provide service to a number of User Equipments (UEs). All UEs are identical and equipped with MIMO antennas, each one of N antenna elements. On the other hand, each RU has a specific capacity of R available resource blocks (RBs) in order to serve the UEs in its coverage area. We also consider that each RU is interconnected with a DU through a fronthaul bus link, with capacity of F bandwidth units (b.u.). Moreover,

the DUs are interconnected with the SDN controller, located at the Near-RT RIC; we assume that for the execution of the appropriate network functions, Data Centers (DCs) are used; we consider that the radio network is supported by a DC with a capacity of C computational resources (c.r.); these resources correspond to CPU and memory resources that can be exploited by the SDN controller at the Regional Edge for executing the network's functions.

The UEs requirements can be categorized into K different service-classes where each service-class k ($k = 1, \dots, K$) has a specific resource requirement of r_k RBs at the RU, f_k b.u. at the fronthaul link and c_k c.r. at the SDN controller. Requests for service from a service-class k arrive at the system according to a Poisson process with arrival rate λ_k while the service time of a request h_k is an exponential random variable with mean value equal to $1/\mu_k$.

When a service-class k UE is connected to the network, resources are occupied both at the radio link and at the fronthaul, while computational resources are also occupied at the SDN controller for the execution of the connection's network functions. In more detail, the following resources are allocated: a) r_k at the RU, b) f_k at the fronthaul, and, c) c_k at the SDN controller. Therefore, we assume that the sequence of the RUs, the fronthaul and the SDN controller is equivalent to as a fixed routing network, where the required resources must be allocated in the joint links. It should be noted that due to the CF nature of the network, when a UE requests service, it may be simultaneously connected to multiple RUs. We assume that there must be available RBs in all connected RUs, in order to serve the UE; otherwise, the request for service is rejected. Thus, we denote the sequence of the RUs, the fronthaul and the computational network elements at the SDN controller as the links that constitute a fixed path P_k . As a consequence, by considering the N RUs which represent the number of RUs that a UE is simultaneously connected, the fronthaul and the SDN controller, the number of links of the path P_k as the assumed routing network is equal to $L = N + 2$.

A. Baseline Scheme

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed network architecture, we utilize the Reduced Load Approximation (RLA) method [12], in order to determine the blocking performance on the equivalent routing network (and therefore at the CF network of Fig. 1). This method aims to calculate the probability that the necessary resources are not available in order to serve a request of a service-class k in a fixed route P_k . By utilizing the RLA method, the Blocking Probability (BP) of a request of a service-class k at a certain link l is defined as follows:

$$Q_k[L_l; a_k, k \in K] = \sum_{j=L_l-b_k+1}^{L_l} G^{-1}q(j) \quad (1)$$

where $a_k = \lambda_k h_k$ is the offered traffic load of service-class k in link l , L_l is the capacity of link l for $l = 1 \dots L$, G is the normalization constant equal to $G = \sum_{j=0}^{L_l} q(j)$ and $q(j)$ is the resource occupancy distribution, which is determined

via the following recursive formula, which is known as the Kaufman-Roberts recursive formula [12]:

$$q(j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } j = 0 \\ \frac{1}{j} \sum_{k=1}^K a_k b_k q(j - b_k), & j = 1, \dots, L_l \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Due to the fact that the required resources must be allocated in a sequence of links in order for the connection establishment to be regarded as successful, the BP expression should be updated, in order to consider the entire set of links of the equivalent routing network. In more detail, we consider that the offered traffic-load of a service-class k to a link is reduced when traversing through a sequence of links. By considering that the offered traffic-load a_k is reduced to $a_k \prod_{i \in P_k - \{l\}} (1 - V_{ik})$, we denote the approximated BP of a service-class k in a specific link l as V_{lk} :

$$V_{lk} = Q_k[L_l; a_k \prod_{i \in P_k - \{l\}} (1 - V_{ik}), k \in K] \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the total BP of a request of a service-class k , B_k , in the entire path P_k is:

$$B_k \approx 1 - \prod_{l \in P_k} (1 - V_{lk}), k = 1 \dots K \quad (4)$$

B. Threshold Scheme

As it is illustrated in Fig.1, the SDN controller receives service-requests from multiple fronthaul links. To avoid connection establishment failure due to the unavailability of computational resources (e.g. during heavy load periods), a resource threshold strategy is proposed for the SDN controller resources. According to the threshold strategy, a service-class k can reduce its resource requirements when the occupied capacity exceeds a predefined resource threshold. By expanding this policy to include multiple thresholds, the resource demand reduction can be executed as many times as the employed thresholds are. By denoting by S the number of resource thresholds, a request of service-class k with initial demand (c_k, μ_k^{-1}) can employ, depending on the occupied link bandwidth, one of the $S + 1$ requirements (c_{ks}, μ_{ks}^{-1}), $s = 0, \dots, S$, where the pair (c_{ks}, μ_{ks}^{-1}) is used when $J_{s-1} < j \leq J_s$ (where $J_{-1} = 0$ and $J_s = C$).

In order to determine the blocking performance of the threshold policy, we adopt the previously described RLA method, which is modified in order to utilize the occupancy distribution $q_T(j)$ of the computational resources in (2) under the threshold policy in the final link of the equivalent network, i.e. in the SDN controller. Therefore, the modified calculation of the blocking probability of a request of a service-class k at the SDN controller is given by:

$$Q_{ks}[C; a_{ks}, k \in K] = \sum_{j=C-c_{ks}+1}^C G^{-1}q(j) \quad (5)$$

In accordance, $q_T(j)$ is calculated as follows [12]:

$$q(j) = \begin{cases} 1, & j = 0 \\ \frac{1}{j} \sum_{k=1}^K a_k c_k \delta_k(j) q(j - c_k) + \\ + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{s=1}^S a_{ks} c_{ks} \delta_{ks}(j) q(j - c_{ks}), & j = 1, \dots, C \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where the term $\delta_k(j)$ is given by:

$$\delta_k(j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{(if } 1 \leq j \leq J_0 + c_k \text{ and } c_{ks} > 0) \text{ or} \\ & \text{(if } 1 \leq j \leq C \text{ and } c_{ks} = 0) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

and the term $\delta_{ks}(j)$ is given by:

$$\delta_{ks}(j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } J_s + c_{ks} \geq j > J_s + c_{ks} \text{ and } b_{ks} > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

C. Overflow scheme

An alternative strategy for the computational-load control that avoids load-requirement reductions is to offload the requests that cannot be serviced by the DC of the SDN controller to another controller. We assume that the offload controller is the FTTH SDN controller of Fig. 1. In particular, we assume that the FTTH SDN controller (alternative system) has a capacity of C_{alt} c.r. and communicates with the SDN controller (primary system) via an SDNi interface, that is used for offloading the overflow traffic. In addition, the FTTH controller also serves requests from K_{alt} service-classes, generated by the supported FTTH users.

The overflow traffic from a primary system to an alternative ceases to be random (i.e. Poisson), thus it is defined by the mean value and the variance of the offered load that is delivered to the alternative system. The mean value M_k of the offered load of a service-class k is determined via:

$$M_k = a_k B_k \quad (9)$$

where $a_k = \lambda_k h_k$ is the traffic-load of service-class k and B_k is the probability that the offered load could not be served in the primary system and it is calculated by (4). For the derivation of the load variance, the number of the necessary resources allocated for the overflow traffic in the alternative system must be known. Specifically, part of the offered load is served at the primary system and the remaining load is delivered to the alternative system. Therefore, we calculate for a service-class k the occupied resources in the primary system (given that a part of the traffic load is rejected) and then we calculate the variance of the traffic that could not be served, based on a procedure presented in [12]. Specifically, the resources allocated for a service-class k in the primary

system are denoted as the resources that are not allocated by the other service-classes:

$$C_k = C - \sum_{i \neq k}^K a_{car,i} c_i \quad (10)$$

where c_i is the resource requirement of a service-class i with $i \neq k$ in the primary system and $a_{car,i}$ is the carried traffic given by:

$$a_{car,i} = a_i (1 - B_i) \quad (11)$$

Having determined the resources occupied from service-class k at the primary system, the variance of the overflow traffic can be defined as follows:

$$\sigma_k^2 = M_k \left(1 - M_k + \frac{a_k}{\frac{C_k}{c_k} + 1 - a_k + M_k} \right) \quad (12)$$

By utilizing the mean value and the variance of the overflow traffic of a service-class k given by (9) and (12) respectively, the peakedness factor Z_k is calculated as follows:

$$Z_k = \frac{\sigma_k^2}{M_k} \quad (13)$$

The value of Z_k denotes the statistical features of the overflow traffic. In more detail, for $Z_k = 1$ it is indicated that the overflow traffic is random, while for $Z_k > 1$ the overflow traffic is characterized as bursty and for $Z_k < 1$ the traffic load is classified as smooth [13].

In respect to the BP calculation at the alternative system due to lack of resources, we consider an approach presented in [13], where an exact formula is proposed and it applies to all types of traffic irrespective of the value of Z_k . Therefore, the probability that the computational resources required from a service-class k (originally at the primary controller) are not available in the FTTH SDN controller is defined by:

$$B_k = \frac{B_k^*}{1 + (Z_k - 1) \cdot (1 - B_k^*)} \quad (14)$$

where the term B_k^* is calculated by:

$$B_k^* = \frac{M_k - a_{mc,k}}{a_{mc,k}} \quad (15)$$

where M_k is given by (9) and $a_{mc,k}$ is the mean carried traffic load in the alternative system given by:

$$a_{mc,k} = \sum_{j=1}^{C_{alt}} \sum_{x=1}^{\lfloor \frac{j}{c_k} \rfloor} \varphi_k \beta_k^{x-1} p(j - x \cdot c_k) \quad (16)$$

with $\lfloor y \rfloor$ denoting the biggest integer not exceeding y . The term φ_k is defined as $\varphi_k = \frac{M_k}{Z_k}$ while the term β_k is equal to $\beta_k = 1 - \frac{1}{Z_k}$. $p(j)$ is the normalized probability that j resources are occupied in the alternative system, determined via:

$$p(j) = \frac{q(j)}{\sum_{j=0}^{C_{alt}} q(j)} \quad (17)$$

where $q(j)$ is the unnormalized resource occupancy distribution:

$$q(j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } j = 0 \\ \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\varphi_k c_k}{j} \sum_{x=1}^{\lfloor \frac{j}{c_k} \rfloor} \beta_k^{x-1} q(j-x \cdot c_k), & j=1, \dots, C_{alt} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

IV. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed system model illustrated in Fig. 1. We consider multi-antenna UEs connecting to the network, requiring for resource allocation in order to be served. In particular, each UE is equipped with $N = 3$ antennas thus it is capable of being connected simultaneously to 3 RUs. Each RU has capacity equal to $R = 300$ RBs and it is interconnected with a DU through a fronthaul link of finite size of $F = 600$ b.u. to the regional network. Moreover, we consider $C = 200$ available c.r. that can be exploited by the SDN controller for executing the network's functions.

Each UE supports $K = 2$ service-classes, each of them requiring network resources in order to initiate a connection. In more detail, the necessary resources for the connection establishment for the 1st service-class are as follows: $r_1 = 5$ RBs in each RU, $f_1 = 15$ b.u. at the fronthaul link and $c_1 = 30$ c.r. at the SDN controller. In accordance, for the 2nd service-class the resources' requirements are: $r_2 = 7$ RBs at the RUs, $f_2 = 21$ b.u. at the fronthaul link and $c_2 = 42$ c.r. at the SDN controller. Since all UEs are connected to multiple RUs simultaneously, it is inferred that for each service-class the required RBs must be available in all RUs during the connection establishment process. However, in case that the required resources are not available, a connection setup failure occurs and the request is blocked. By utilizing the method expanded on Section III.A, the BP of the two service-classes are presented in the second column of Table I and Table II, respectively, for the baseline scenario, versus the offered traffic load. The latter is expressed by traffic points provided in the the first column of Table I and Table II: point 1 is ($a_1 = 1$ erl, $a_2 = 2$ erl) while the consecutive points are increased by 0.5 erl for both service-classes, thus point 10 is ($a_1 = 5.5$ erl, $a_2 = 6.5$ erl).

To avoid the connection establishment failure, the threshold scheme was proposed according to which the application's demand is reduced at the expense of a greater service time and by extension a higher traffic load. In the proposed threshold scheme we consider $S = 2$ thresholds for the computational resources at the SDN controller and their values are different for each service-class, which are calculated as $J_{S-1} = C - 4c_{kS-1}$. For the 1st service-class the computational requirements are reduced from $c_{10} = c_1 = 30$ c.r., to $c_{11} = 15$ c.r. and to $c_{12} = 12$ c.r., for the two thresholds, respectively, while for the 2nd service-class, the corresponding requirements are $c_{20} = c_2 = 42$ c.r., $c_{21} = 25$ c.r. and $c_{22} = 22$ c.r. It should be noted that the service times of both service-classes are reduced proportionally to the requirements' increase. Furthermore, the

load-thresholds are as defined follows: for the 1st service-class: $J_s = \{80,140\}$ and for the 2nd service-class: $J_s = \{32,100\}$ where $s = 0, 1$. The BP of both service-classes are calculated by exploiting the method described in Section III.B and presented at the third column of Table I and Table II for the two service-classes, respectively. As the comparison with the baseline strategy results reveal, the threshold strategy results in significant lower BP values; however, this reduction is achieved when the demands have been reduced, which is reflected to an increased service-time.

For the evaluation of the overflow strategy, we consider an alternative system, which is expressed by the FTTH SDN controller illustrated in Fig. 1. This alternative system provides service to both the overflow traffic from the primary SDN controller, as well as to traffic generated by the UEs that are connected to this controller. In more detail, the alternative system has capacity equal to $C_{alt} = 400$ c.r. and it provides computational resources to $K_{alt} = 2$ service-classes. The 1st service-class requires $c_{alt1} = 15$ c.r. in order to be served, while the 2nd service-class requires $c_{alt2} = 25$ c.r. The requests of both service-classes arrive at the system according to a Poisson process. As a consequence, the alternative system serves in general the requests of $K = 4$ different service-classes (2 of its own UEs and 2 due to the overflow procedure). By utilizing the method portrayed in Section III.C, the probability is calculated that the necessary resources are not available even after the overflow procedure. The results for the two service-classes are featured on the fourth column of Table I and Table II, for the two service-classes, respectively. As it is anticipated, when the overflow alternative is applied, the probabilities of not establishing a connection are hugely reduced and their values remain in an acceptable level despite the increase of the offered load. This outcome stands on the fact that the capacity of the alternative system is significantly higher indicating that more resources are available to exploit.

The proposed analysis can be also used in order to determine the minimum number of resources that the proposed system must provide in order to execute the network's functions, while keeping the BP under a predefined level. Fig. 2, illustrates the minimum controller capacity that is required in order to support request with a BP lower than 1% for both service-classes, for the baseline and the threshold strategies, versus the traffic load. The latter is expressed by the same traffic-load points as in Table I and Table II. As it is was anticipated, as the offered traffic is increased, the minimum capacity of the controller also increases, while the capacity values are higher under the baseline strategy compared to the threshold strategy. This is justified by the fact that in the threshold scheme the requirement reduction results in a lower BP compared to the corresponding probability in the baseline scheme. As a consequence, in the threshold scheme the desired Grade of Service (GoS) can be obtained by utilizing fewer resources. It should be noted similar results can be obtained for the overflow strategy; however, they are not compared with the corresponding results of the two other strategies, as its results is highly affected by the capacity of the alternative controller.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a mathematical framework for the performance evaluation of strategies that are applied for controlling the computational load in cell-free-based, converged optical-wireless 6G networks. The proposed analysis targets to reduce the probability that a service request cannot be accepted due to the unavailability of computational resources. To this end, two strategies are proposed, namely the threshold strategy and the overflow strategy, that target to reduce the blocking probabilities compared to a baseline scenario, where no load control is applied. The proposed analysis can be also used for the determination of the minimum computational resources that are required at the controller, so that the blocking performance does not exceed pre-defined levels. In our future work we target to study more sophisticated strategies that are based on balancing the load on the two controllers, targeting to improve the utilization of the computational resources.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been funded by the research projects H2020-ICT-2018-20 MARSAL (101017171), and MSCA-RISE EXPLOR (872897).

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TABLE I
BLOCKING PROBABILITY OF THE 1st SERVICE-CLASS ESTIMATED USING THREE PROPOSED FORMALISMS FOR TEN LOAD POINTS

Traffic load point	BP of the baseline strategy	BP of the threshold strategy	BP of the overflow strategy
1	9.28%	1.58%	$7.96 \times 10^{-4}\%$
2	17.30%	3.99%	$5.42 \times 10^{-3}\%$
3	25.08%	7.37%	$2.20 \times 10^{-2}\%$
4	31.97%	11.29%	$6.52 \times 10^{-2}\%$
5	37.87%	15.38%	0.16%
6	42.89%	19.43%	0.38%
7	47.15%	23.29%	0.79%
8	50.80%	26.90%	1.56%
9	53.95%	30.27%	2.96%
10	56.69%	33.38%	5.50%

TABLE II
BLOCKING PROBABILITY OF THE 2nd SERVICE-CLASS ESTIMATED USING THREE PROPOSED FORMALISMS FOR TEN LOAD POINTS

Traffic load point	BP of the baseline strategy	BP of the threshold strategy	BP of the overflow strategy
1	13.41%	3.42%	$9.96 \times 10^{-3}\%$
2	22.40%	8.14%	$3.08 \times 10^{-2}\%$
3	31.03%	14.36%	$7.35 \times 10^{-2}\%$
4	38.66%	21.19%	0.15%
5	45.19%	27.96%	0.29%
6	50.72%	34.31%	0.57%
7	55.42%	40.09%	1.08%
8	59.42%	45.27%	1.96%
9	62.86%	49.87%	3.45%
10	65.83%	53.96%	5.86%

Fig. 2. Controller capacity vs traffic load for the baseline and threshold strategies.